

THE BENEFITS OF MOBILE PHONES IN IMPROVING ENGLISH LANGUAGE SPEAKING

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays it is crucial to learn at least one foreign language in order to be successful in one's career and life. Speaking is, of course, the most important skill since it shows how a user is competitive in the language they speak. It is hard to imagine language learning without the participation of mobile phones today. This article discusses the importance of mobile phones in learning English and improving speaking skills.

***keywords:** mobile devices, mobile technologies, English, application, information technologies.*

INTRODUCTION

The modern period of development of society is characterized by the influence of information technologies on it, which penetrate into all spheres of human activity, ensure the dissemination of information flows in society, and form a global information space. An integral and important part of the informatization of society is the informatization of education. At the moment, there are about one and a half billion mobile phones in the world, which is three times more than traditional computers [4].

As technology progresses, mobile devices receive new technical capabilities, the speed and reliability of data transmission in wireless communication channels increases. Mobile phones, smartphones, tablet computers are becoming the main part of a person's digital life. According to available data, over the past five years, the number of teenagers who know how to use a computer, mobile information technology has increased by about ten times. At present, almost everyone has mobile devices, it is a convenient tool for accessing any information, in particular, educational type. Students are poorly aware of the potential educational opportunities provided by

smartphones, communicators and tablet computers. As revealed in many studies, adolescents are mainly familiar with gaming computer and mobile programs and applications, use mobile phones and computer equipment for entertainment. At the same time, cognitive, in particular educational, motives for working with a computer are approximately in twentieth place [6].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This topic was touched upon by such domestic researchers as E.V. Vulfovich [2], I.N. Golitsyna, N.L. Polovnikova [3], N.V. Samokhina [5] and others. This problem was studied by such foreign researchers as K. Betti, V.M. Frank, S. Freinik, D. Richardson, etc.

Studying the discipline "Foreign language" (FL) using mobile devices is a relatively new way of studying it, which is gaining popularity among many users of smartphones and tablet computers [1]. Teaching English (EL) assumes that the process will be continuous, which means that learning with the help of mobile information technologies, using gadgets, helps to improve the quality and intensity of learning for a set of free access to mobile information technologies. Thus, there are many methods of teaching a foreign language, in particular, a foreign language, involving the use of information technologies and technical means, providing a high informative capacity of educational material, stimulating the cognitive activity of students, increasing the visibility of the lesson, the intensity of its implementation, individualization and differentiation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The word English cannot be used without communication. In multi-lingual countries like India, English occupies the foremost position in use of communication. English communication should be needed for the following reasons: finding a first-rate employment, communicating with the international world and accessing sources in the student's major fields. The better communication one must have the best proficiency. Pronunciation is a way of speaking a word, especially a way that is accepted or generally understood. The main problem is because of our mother tongue influence and

lack in teaching pronunciation in the educational institutions. English skills are learned after the great effort of the learners.

Invention of android mobile phones helps the learners to achieve their requirements. In the field of education all the universities offer the degrees in English. All the materials are in English language. The learners must have good English skills to read the book. When they are asked to present the content matters they are using the language with their mother tongue influence. So the learners must practice the Standard English. By using these application and continuous practice definitely one can achieve good pronunciation skill. It is sure that these applications will make them as Standard English speakers. These dictionaries are ideal for everyone who needs a comprehensive and authoritative dictionary of current English, for professionals, students, academics, and for use at work or at home. It is practical and easy to use and the students learn more by doing. It increases time on learning and promotes academic skills. It improves performance on standardized tests and speech and increases student learning opportunities. The teachers play a minor role in learning the English pronunciation skills and teacher can monitor student performance.

Among the well-known mobile applications focused on the study of EL are Learn English Elementary [2], Duolingo applications [6], Memrise [3], Grammar Up [1], LangBook, etc. gram for memorizing words LinguaLeo [1], etc.

Applications Learn English Elementary is a series of podcasts for learners of English that can be downloaded to mobile phones and studied at any time convenient for the user. Each episode lasts approximately twenty minutes and is accompanied by questions for listeners. To facilitate understanding, a "running line" is provided.

With the free Duolingo app, you can learn both EL and Italian, French, Spanish, German, Portuguese. It can be used as a supplementary guide with interactive exercises for learners of EL from scratch. An Internet connection is required to download the next stage of interactive lessons. The educational course is divided into stages according to the principle "from simple to complex". The Duolingo educational app

trains skills such as writing and speaking (you will be prompted to pronounce the studied phrases), reading and listening.

The Memrise educational mobile application, with which you can learn both AL and many other languages, is a continuation of the website of the same name. This application has an intuitive interface, which in turn allows the user to immediately start learning a foreign language. Learning new words with the help of images, practical interactive tasks for repetition and consolidation contribute to more effective learning of vocabulary.

The Grammar Up application is designed for those students who periodically experience difficulties in constructing foreign language sentences, using articles and other grammatical difficulties. The educational program contains rules and examples of use. The student is given the opportunity to take the test, consolidating and replenishing the vocabulary of words. This application also has a version of Phrasal Verbs Lite, which allows you to practice conversational AP using idioms and phrasal verbs.

The LangBook educational app can be used for traditional translation as well as teaching. This educational application offers users a thesaurus, explanatory, encyclopedic, geographical, engineering and many other dictionaries. For example, the application contains a dictionary with a translator, user tools for learning a foreign language and memorizing difficult words. The creators of the LangBook application organized the download of dictionaries and the sounding of words at the request of the user. In addition, the application helps to learn a foreign language with the help of interactive cards with educational tasks, well-structured and divided into educational topics. The main purpose of the program is to perform the functions of a dictionary. By default, only the English-Uzbek and Uzbek-English dictionaries are installed in the application, which include about a million words. The translator built into the program makes it possible to transliterate not only sentences, but also entire texts. In order for the translation to be the most accurate, the user is advised to specify the subject of the text manually. A feature of the program is that it can work offline.

The program for memorizing words LinguaLeo offers four types of training: word-translation, translation-word, word constructor, listening. The application is integrated with a website that allows you to learn foreign words, read, listen to educational texts, and solve crossword puzzles. All words to be studied on the site become available in the mobile version as well.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the proposed approach to the organization of learning EL using mobile devices not only continues the previously established traditions of learning EL using technical devices, but also expands them through the use of fundamentally new capabilities of mobile platforms. It expands the learning environment of FL, taking it beyond the limits of a computer application and even a computer network. The experience gained in using the proposed educational mobile technologies has shown their feasibility and effectiveness in modern realizable educational practice. At the same time, the teaching of a foreign language, in particular, the English Language, using mobile information technologies, is realized in the form of an independent and game activity, which in turn contributes to the successful development of a foreign language.

REFERENCES

1. *English with Lingualeo.* – 2016
2. *Vulfovich E.V. The role of mobile learning in the optimization of teaching foreign languages / E.V. Vulfovich // Proceedings of the Volgograd State Pedagogical University.* - 2014. - No. 6 (91). - S. 161-164.
3. *Golitsyna I.N. Mobile learning as a new technology in education / I.N. Golitsyna, N.L. Polovnikova // Educational technologies and society.* - 2011. - S. 241-252.
4. *Dedova O.V. About the language of the Internet / O.V. Dedova // Bulletin of Moscow State University. Ser. 9. Philology.* - 2017. - No. 3. – P. 25–38.
5. *Samokhina N.V. The use of mobile technologies in teaching English: the development of traditions and the search for new methodological models / N.V. Samokhina // Fundamental research.* - 2014. - No. 6. – S. 591–595.
6. *Modern information technologies in education // GOU VPO "Shui State Pedagogical University".* – 2016